

Evaluation of Dialysis Adequacy and Its Effect on Short-Term Morbidity and Mortality.

(A cross-sectional observational study)

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ABSTRACT

Background

Dialysis adequacy is commonly measured by Kt/V and plays a crucial role in reducing morbidity and mortality. Online Clearance Monitoring (OCM) offers a real-time, non-invasive method to measure Kt/V and enhance treatment outcomes.

Materials and methods

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted on maintenance hemodialysis patients over four months. Dialysis adequacy was assessed using Kt/V values obtained by Online

Clearance Monitoring (OCM) integrated into Fresenius 4008S HD machines. Mean Kt/V was calculated by adding all Kt/V values recorded during each dialysis session over 4 months at weekly and monthly intervals and dividing by the number of sessions accordingly. Patient's demographics, clinical characteristics, and details of dialysis sessions were recorded. Biochemical, nutritional, and dialysis-specific parameters were evaluated to assess the association between Kt/V levels and patient outcomes. Short-term morbidity was monitored through hospitalization and clinical events, while mortality data were collected throughout the study.

Result

The total number of patients in this study was 20 out of which 14 were males and 6 were females. We recorded 10 patients with Kt/v greater than or equal to 1.2 and 10 patients with Kt/V less than 1.2. The average age of patients in the adequate group was 32.6 ± 10.42 (ranging 20 to 54), while the average age of patients in the inadequate group was 39.5 ± 9.36 (ranging 22 to 58). There was significance difference between the BSA($p = 0.00478$), BFR (0.0067), and DFR(0.0098) of these 2 groups. Hospitalizations were more frequent in the inadequate group (5 vs. 1), and deaths were also higher (2 vs. 1), with inadequate dialysis.

Conclusion

Inadequate dialysis is associated with an increased risk of short-term hospitalization and mortality in patients undergoing hemodialysis.

Keywords: Dialysis Adequacy, Kt/V, Online Clearance Monitoring, Morbidity and Mortality, Hospitalization, Inadequate dialysis.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease is a long-term disorder that affects over 10% of the global population (approximately 800 million people), with prevalence in India varying by region from less than 1% to 17%, and more than 2 million people worldwide are being treated for ESRD [1,2,3].

Hemodialysis is the most common treatment for these patients, who typically visit clinics two to three times a week for three to four hours per session.[4,5] Patients on maintenance HD have a higher risk of death, which is impacted by a variety of factors such as nutritional status, dialysis effectiveness, and existing health issues such as diabetes, HTN, ischemic disease [6]. Inadequate nutritional status, along with factors like lack of appetite, food restrictions, and depression, contributes significantly to illness and mortality in CKD patients [7,8].

Adequacy of dialysis describes how effectively toxins and waste products are cleared from the bloodstream, and it plays a crucial role in influencing both morbidity and mortality rates.[9,10].

Dialysis adequacy is determined by Kt/V , with

K represents dialyzer urea clearance, which varies based on Dialysate flow rate (DFR), dialyzer size, and Blood Flow Rate (BFR).

Dialysis time (t) commonly ranges from 180-240 minutes [11,12].

The volume of distribution for urea (V) [13].

The effective adequate dose of Kt/V is 1.2 - 1.4 for every dialysis session [14]. When Kt/V falls below 0.8, it is correlated with increased morbidity or treatment failure, whereas a Kt/V greater than 1.0 is related to better outcomes [15]. A reduction of 0.1 in Kt/V is thought to raise the mortality risk by 7% [16].

This study assesses the effect of dialysis adequacy on morbidity and mortality with the use of OCM in evaluating Kt/V [6]. The 4008S HD machine from Fresenius Medical Care, Germany, is integrated with an OCM menu that accepts age in years, height in cm, dry weight in kg, gender, hematocrit (HCT), and goal Kt/V [17,18]. In OCM systems, urea concentration in wasted dialysate is continuously measured by ultraviolet (UV) absorbance [19].

Dialysis dose (Kt/V) is influenced by various elements such as treatment duration (TT), BFR, DFR, and interruptions during sessions (such as hypotension or clotting), the dialyzer, and precise techniques for blood sampling also influence it [20]. Currently, cardiovascular disease and inadequate dialysis remain the primary factors contributing to illness and death in patients undergoing hemodialysis. Other risk factors include arterial hypertension, diabetes, obesity,

malnutrition, anemia, poor treatment adherence, and various types of vascular access [21].

This research will examine the impact of dialysis adequacy on the incidence of illness and death among patients undergoing hemodialysis [22].

Materials & Methods

This study was carried out as a cross-sectional observational research within a clinical environment. within a hospital setting. It was conducted in the Hemodialysis unit of the Department of Nephrology, NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan, for 4 months, from the month of January 2025 to April 2025.

All the patients on MHD, coming to our department for hemodialysis sessions, were recruited for the study according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The Inclusion Criteria are Patients above 18 years old who receive a 4-hour session at least twice a week, stable arteriovenous fistula, graft, and central venous catheter access. (Able to give at least 250ml/min blood flow), undergoing MHD for over three months, clinically stable with no evidence of chronic or acute infection and malignancy. The Exclusion Criteria are Patients above 70 years old, treatment with single needle dialysis, all extracorporeal procedures except hemodialysis, hemodynamically unstable patients at the time of recruitment, patients with proven cardiovascular disorders / Cerebrovascular disorders,/ Chronic liver disease.

Baseline Data Collection of the enrolled patients was gathered, which included: Age, Gender, Length and frequency of dialysis, Primary renal condition, vascular access, Height & dry weight, HD vintage, Type of dialyzer and its surface area. All patients undergo hemodialysis sessions twice a week, with each session lasting 4 hours, using an F6HPS polysulfone dialyzer with a surface area of 1.3 square meters. We calculated the mean Kt/V of each patient. The Mean Kt/V was calculated by adding all Kt/V values recorded during each dialysis session over 4 months at weekly and monthly intervals and dividing by the number of sessions accordingly. Kt/V values were obtained using Online Clearance Monitoring (OCM) on a Fresenius 4008s machine.

Based on dialysis adequacy, patients were categorized into two groups: the adequate group and the inadequate group. Investigations to evaluate the morbidity and mortality between these two groups include an assessment of Hematological, Biochemical, pathological, Nutritional,

physiological, and hemodialysis Parameters, which affect the Kt/v, were conducted continuously for 4 months at regular intervals.

The total no. of patients (n) is 20. The sample size was based on convenience sampling. Data was entered in MS EXCEL 2019. Data was analyzed using software SPSS v25. Mean and standard deviation were used for the continuous variable. Independent and dependent sample t-tests, and the Chi-square test were done, and the p-value was calculated to find a significant difference between the 2 groups.

Observation & Result

A total of 20 patients participated in the study, with baseline characteristics provided in Table 2. The causes of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) included hypertensive nephropathy (n=7), glomerulonephritis (n=2), congenital issues (n=3), diabetic nephropathy (n=3), nephrolithiasis (n=2), and nephrotic syndrome (n=3).

Measuring achieved Kt/V confirms dialysis adequacy and ensures accurate group classification, are described in Table 2. It also helps compare outcomes and guide treatment improvements.

Month		Adequate group	Inadequate group	t-test	P-Value	Significance
1	Mean achieved Kt/V	1.56 ± 0.26	1.14 ± 0.11	4.7	0.0002	significant
2	Mean achieved Kt/V	1.45 ± 0.17	1.12 ± 0.09	5.43	< 0.001	significant
3	Mean achieved Kt/V	1.48 ± 0.22	1.11 ± 0.04	5.23	0.0001	significant
4	Mean achieved Kt/V	1.42 ± 0.22	1.13 ± 0.06	4.02	0.0008	significant

TABLE 1: - Mean achieved Kt/V

- There was significance difference between the achieved Kt/V of adequate group and inadequate group patients.

GRAPH 1: - Mean achieved Kt/V

This study found 10 patients with Kt/V greater than or equal to 1.2 and 10 patients with Kt/V less than 1.2. The total number of patients in the adequate group ($Kt/V \geq 1.2$) was 10, with 6 males and 4 females, and the total number of patients in the inadequate group ($Kt/V < 1.2$) was 10, with 8 males and 2 females. The average age of patients in the adequate group was 32.6 ± 10.42 (with a range of 20 to 54), while the average age of patients in the inadequate group was 39.5 ± 9.36 (with a range of 22 to 58). The adequate group had 10 patients with left AVF, while the inadequate group had 8 with left AVF and 2 with right AVF. The mean BSA of patients in the adequate group was 1.37 ± 0.13 (ranging 1.2-1.6), and the mean BSA of the inadequate group patients was 1.55 ± 0.12 (ranging 1.3-1.7). There was significance difference between the BSA of these 2 groups from the start of the study ($p=0.00478$).

Baseline characteristic	Adequate group	Inadequate group
Group division based on dialysis adequacy (Kt/V)	10	10
	male: 6	male: 8
	female: 4	female: 2
Vascular access	Left AVF: 10 Right AVF:0	Left AVF:2 Right AVF:8
Mean age of patients	32.6 ± 10.42 (ranging 20 to 54)	39.5 ± 9.36 (ranging 22-58)
HD vintage	3.6 ± 1.71 (ranging 2-7)	3.0 ± 1.89 (ranging 1-6)
BSA (meter square)	1.37 ± 0.13 (rangigng 1.2-1.6)	1.55 ± 0.12 (ranging 1.3-1.7)

TABLE 2: Baseline characteristics of patients

Investigations to evaluate the morbidity and mortality between these two groups include biochemical and nutritional parameters, which are Hb, TLC, serum urea, creatinine, phosphate, potassium, calcium, total protein, albumin, BMI, and SGA. The dialysis parameters, which are

BFR, DFR, Kt/V, dialyzer fiber bundle volume, pre-dialysis b.p., and dry weight also studied for 4 months, which is represented with mean \pm standard deviation in Table 3.

Clinical Parameters	Adequate group	Inadequate group	P-Value
1. Dialysis Parameters			
Dry weight (kg)	43.82 \pm 7.075	52.56 \pm 7.46	0.0165
BFR (ml/min)	326.4 \pm 26.362	271.3 \pm 26.127	0.0003
DFR (ml/min)	650 \pm 158	500 \pm 0	0.0098
FBV (%)	90.43 \pm 1.55	90.18 \pm 1.29	0.5247
Pre HD DBP (mmHg)	91.75 \pm 8.54	96 \pm 9.295	0.3025
Pre HD SBP (mmHg)	157 \pm 20.807	169.75 \pm 17.815	0.1727
2. Biochemical Parameters			
Hb (g/dl)	8.6 \pm 2.35	7.9 \pm 1.19	0.4010
TLC (ths/ul)	6.25 \pm 2.69	6.75 \pm 1.93	0.6586
S. Urea(mg/dl)	136.75 \pm 50.60	144 \pm 36.16	0.6124
S. Cr(mg/dl)	10.95 \pm 2.64	10.77 \pm 2.23	0.7074
S. Calcium (mg/dl)	7.8 \pm 0.9	8.4 \pm 0.64	0.1816
S. Phosphorus (mg/dl)	5.9 \pm 2.71	6.4 \pm 2.62	0.7243
S. potassium (mmol/l)	5.3 \pm 0.73	5.415 \pm 0.85	0.5671
3. Nutritional Parameters			
BMI (kg /meter square)	17.53 \pm 2.98	18.67 \pm 1.83	0.3200
S. Albumin (g/dl)	4.22 \pm 0.38	3.86 \pm 0.56	0.1934
Total Protein (g/dl)	7.07 \pm 0.45	6.70 \pm 0.57	0.1495

TABLE 3: Clinical Parameters of patients

1. Dialysis Parameters: In dialysis parameters, a significance difference was seen in BFR ($p = 0.0003$), dry weight ($p = 0.0165$), and DFR ($p = 0.0098$) between the groups. A total of 10 patients in the adequate group, out of which 5 patients achieved 300ml/min BFR, and 5 patients achieved 350ml/min BFR while in the inadequate group of 10 patients, out of which 5 patients should achieve 250 ml/min BFR, and 5 patients should achieve 300 ml/min BFR. The inadequate group of all 10 patients achieved 500 ml/min DFR. The total of 10 patients in the adequate group, out of which 5 patients achieved 500ml/min DFR, and 5 patients achieved 800ml/min DFR. There was no significance difference seen in dialyzer fiber bundle volume ($p = 0.5247$), and pre-HD SBP ($P = 0.1727$) and DBP ($p = 0.3025$).

GRAPH 2: Dialysis Parameters

2. Biochemical Parameters: There was no significance difference seen in biochemical parameters between these 2 groups. This includes Hb, TLC ($p = 0.6586$), S. urea ($p = 0.6124$), S. creatinine ($p = 0.7074$), S. calcium ($p = 0.1816$), S. phosphorus($p = 0.7243$), and S. potassium ($p = 0.5671$) described in graph 3.

GRAPH 3: Biochemical Parameters

3. Nutritional Parameters: There was no significance difference seen in nutritional parameters between these two groups. This includes S. BMI ($p = 0.3200$), S. albumin ($p = 0.1934$), and total protein($p = 0.1495$). SGA was also used for the evaluation of nutritional health in

hemodialysis patients. The inadequate dialysis group often shows worse scores due to toxin buildup, while the adequate dialysis group supports better nutrition.

GRAPH 4: Nutritional Parameters

4. Evaluation of morbidity and mortality: To evaluate morbidity risk between patients in the adequate group and inadequate group, three criteria were used to assess morbidity. These criteria, in an improved and organized format, are as follows:
- Incidence of Infections: Incidence of infections was higher in the inadequate group of patients as compared to patients in the adequate group.
 - Need for Blood Transfusion: The Number of Blood transfusions was higher in the inadequate group of patients.
 - Incidence of Emergency Admissions: The Incidence of emergency admissions was higher in the inadequate group. The most common causes are fluid overload and shortness of breath.
 - Incidence of death: Remarkably, there was 1 death recorded in the adequate group and 2 in the inadequate group.

Below is a table 4 summarizing the incidence rates for each criterion:

criteria	Adequate	Inadequate
Incidence of infection	1	1
Need for blood transfusion	0	3
Incidence of emergency admission	1	5
Incidence of death	1	2

TABLE 4: Morbidity and mortality

Discussion

Assessing the adequacy of dialysis is a fundamental aspect for improving patients' Quality of Life (QoL) suffering from ESRD. Proper nutrition and HD dosage can significantly reduce the rates of illness and death in individuals undergoing dialysis.

Patients who achieved higher adequacy metrics demonstrated fewer hospital admissions, lower incidence of fluid overload and electrolyte imbalance, and reduced mortality within the observed period.

This study showed that patients' group achieving adequate dialysis ($Kt/V \geq 1.2$) was related to decreased morbidity and death. A previous study also revealed the same results that high dialysis dose (Kt/V) is associated with an increased survival rate [23]. This study also found that Males are more likely to have inadequate dialysis. Eighty percent of males receive inadequate dialysis, compared to 20% of females. A prior study indicated that no significant difference in dialysis adequacy based on gender [24].

There was significance difference observed in BFR ($p = 0.0003$) and DFR ($p = 0.0098$) in both groups. Higher BFR is associated with high Kt/V . Another study indicates that higher eBFR (>275 mL/min) is linked to a decreased risk of new major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) and all-cause death compared to lower eBFR (≤ 275 mL/min) [25]. Higher DFR corresponds with higher Kt/V . A study found that increasing the dialysate flow rate from twice the blood flow rate, or from 500 mL/min to 700 mL/min, led to relative gains in Kt/V , suggesting that a dialysate flow rate of 700 mL/min is primarily related to improved dialysis adequacy [26]. From the start of the study, there was significance difference noted in BSA ($p=0.00478$) between these two groups. Kt/V increased as the body surface area decreased. One study indicates that the Kt/BSA ratio, which adjusts for body surface area, may be essential

for more accurately assessing the dose of hemodialysis [27]. There was no significance difference ($p=0.32$) between the body mass index of adequate group and inadequate group patients. A prior study identified a significant connection between BMI and dialysis adequacy ($P = 0.004$), with 54 (60%) obese individuals having inadequate dialysis [28]. There was no significance difference in fiber bundle volume between adequate and inadequate groups, but FBV strongly correlated with Kt/V ($r = 0.86$). Prior study findings indicated a significant difference between using a new dialyzer and a reused dialyzer ($\alpha = 0.037$, $p < 0.05$) [29].

The study found that the incidence of emergency hospitalization was 10 out of 1 in the adequate group and 10 out of 5 in the inadequate group. There was an increased incidence of blood transfusion in the inadequate group compared to the adequate group. The study shows that the incidence of infection was 10 out of 1 for patients in the adequate group and 10 out of 1 for patients in the inadequate group. The study reveals that the incidence of death was 10 out of 1 in the adequate group and 10 out of 2 in the inadequate group. There was one death in the adequate group; she was recorded as malnourished during the study, and other reasons for her death are unclear, which were most likely unrelated to dialysis adequacy. In contrast, two patients in the inadequate group died due to suboptimal dialysis with low Kt/V—one from cardiac arrest and the other from a brain stroke. A previous study also revealed the same results, that insufficient dialysis (low Kt/V) is probably associated with a higher mortality rate among patients undergoing dialysis [22]. The study indicated that raising the dialysis dosage decreases the likelihood of hospitalization and death among individuals receiving hemodialysis [30].

Conclusion

Findings of this study highlight the therapeutic significance of establishing and maintaining dialysis adequacy in lowering short-term morbidity and mortality. Strategies to improve dialysis adequacy may include increasing blood flow rate, using a larger dialyzer, extending the duration of dialysis sessions, optimizing needle size and placement, and reassessing arteriovenous (AV) access function.

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